

Impact Factor: 5.19

ISSN: 2181-0664

DOI: 10.26739/2181-0664

www.tadqiqot.uz

UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

Volume 4, Issue 4

2023

ISSN 2181-0664

Doi Journal 10.26739/2181-0664

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

4 ЖИЛД, 4 СОН

УЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ

ТОМ 4, НОМЕР 4

UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

VOLUME 4, ISSUE 4

ТОШКЕНТ-2023

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЎЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ | UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

№4 (2023) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-0664-2023-4>

Бош мухаррир:
Главный редактор:
Chief Editor:

Мадазимов Мадамин Муминович
Ректор Андижанского Государственного
медицинского института, д.м.н., профессор
кафедры факультетской и госпитальной
хирургии

Тахририят раиси:
Председатель редакционной коллегии:
Chairman of the editorial Board:

Алексеев Андрей Анатольевич
Директор ожогового центра НМИЦ хирургии
им. В.Вишневого, главный комбустиолог
Министерства здравоохранения России, д.м.н.,
профессор.

Бош мухаррир ўринбосари:
Заместитель главного редактора:
Deputy Chief Editor:

Салахиддинов Камалиддин Зухриддинович
доцент, д.м.н. кафедры факультетской и
госпитальной хирургии Андижанского
Государственного медицинского института

Бош мухаррир ўринбосари:
Заместитель главного редактора:
Deputy Chief Editor:

Хегай Любовь Николаевна
доцент, к.м.н., начальник отдела по координации
деятельности грантов Межвузовской научно-
исследовательской лаборатории Ташкентской
медицинской академии

Маъсул котиб:
Ответственный секретарь:
Executive Secretary:

Досина Маргарита Олеговна
в.н.с. ГНУ "Институт физиологии Национальной
академии наук Беларуси", к.б.н., председатель
Совета молодых ученых Отделения медицинских
наук НАН Беларуси

Маъсул котиб:
Ответственный секретарь:
Executive Secretary:

Ниязова Зебинисо Анваровна
PhD кафедры офтальмологии, детской
офтальмологии Ташкентского педиатрического
медицинского института

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ ТАХРИРИЙ МАСЛАХАТ КЕНГАШИ | РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ СОВЕТ ЎЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ EDITORIAL BOARD OF THE UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

Хужамбердиев Мамазоир Ахмедович

д.м.н., профессор кафедры госпитальной терапии Андижанского Государственного медицинского института

Привалова Ирина Леонидовна

д.б.н., профессор кафедры нормальной физиологии Курского государственного медицинского университета,
заведующая лабораторией физиологии висцеральных систем НИИ физиологии (Курск)

Гаврилова Елена Анатольевна

д.м.н., профессор, заведующая кафедрой лечебной физкультуры и спортивной медицины Северо-западного
государственного медицинского университета им. И.И. Мечникова (Санкт-Петербург)

Чурганов Олег Анатольевич

д.п.н., профессор кафедры ЛФК и спортивной медицины Северо-Западного государственного
медицинского университета им. И.И. Мечникова (Санкт-Петербург)

Салахиддинов Зухриддин Салахиддинович

д.м.н., профессор, заведующий кафедрой ВОП №1, Андижанского государственного медицинского института

Рябчиков Денис Анатольевич

д.м.н., в.н.с. онкологического отделения хирургических методов лечения ФГБУ "НМИЦ
онкологии им. Н.Н. Блохина" Минздрава России

Гулямов Суръат Саидвалиевич

д.м.н., профессор кафедры оториноларингологии, детской оториноларингологии, стоматологии
Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Тереза Магалхайз
профессор, заведующая кафедрой Судебной медицины государственного университета Порту (Португалия)

Юлдашев Илхом Рузиевич
д.м.н., профессор, заведующий кафедрой Аллергологии, иммунологии, микробиологии
Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Хамраев Абдурашид Журакулович
д.м.н., профессор кафедры госпитальной детской хирургии, Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

РЕДАКЦИОННАЯ КОЛЛЕГИЯ:

Эрматов Низом Жумакулович
д.м.н., доцент, заведующий кафедрой гигиены детей и подростков и гигиены питания Ташкентской медицинской академии

Рузиев Шерзод Ибодуллаевич
д.м.н., доцент кафедры судебной медицины и медицинского права Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Якубова Олтиной Абдуганиевна
доктор медицинских наук, доцент, заведующая кафедрой акушерства и гинекологии, неонатологии факультета повышения квалификации и переподготовки врачей Андижанского государственного медицинского института

Бабич Светлана Михайловна
доцент, заведующая кафедрой социальной гигиены Андижанского государственного медицинского института

Сабирова Рихси Абдукадировна
д.м.н., профессор кафедры медицинской и биологической химии Ташкентской медицинской академии

Цеомашко Наталья Евгеньевна
д.б.н., с.н.с., заведующая отделом медико-генетических исследований МНИЛ Ташкентской медицинской академии

Хамраева Лола Салимовна
доцент, к.м.н. кафедры офтальмологии, детской офтальмологии Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Усманходжаева Адиба Амирсаидовна
доцент, к.м.н., заведующая кафедрой Народной медицины, реабилитологии и физической культуры Ташкентской медицинской академии

Тухтаева Нигора Хасановна
DSc, доцент кафедры пропедевтики внутренних болезней № 2, Ташкентской медицинской академии.

Шарипова Фарида Камилевна
к.м.н., доцент кафедры психиатрии, наркологии и детской психиатрии, медицинской психологии, психотерапии
Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Бузруков Батир Тулкунович
д.м.н., профессор, заведующий кафедрой офтальмологии, детской офтальмологии Ташкентского педиатрического
медицинского института

Туйчиев Галибжан Урмонжонович
к.м.н., доцент, заведующий кафедрой детской хирургии, детской анестезиологии-реаниматологии с курсом
офтальмологии и стоматологии факультета усовершенствования и переподготовки врачей АГМИ

Маматхужаева Гулнора Нажмитдиновна
доцент, к.м.н. кафедры Офтальмологии Андижанского Государственного медицинского института

Каримова Зиёда Кушбаевна
доцент, к.м.н. кафедры Аллергологии, клинической иммунологии, микробиологии Ташкентского педиатрического
медицинского института

Саидходжаева Саида Набиевна
доцент, Phd кафедры неврологии, детской неврологии и медицинской генетики Ташкентского педиатрического
медицинского института

Зуфарова Зухра Хабибуллаевна
доцент, к.ф.н. кафедры промышленной технологии лекарственных средств Ташкентского фармацевтического института

Ибрагимова Марина Фёдоровна
PhD, ассистент кафедры N1 педиатрии и неонатологии Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета.

Алимова Дурдона Дильмуратовна
PhD кафедры оториноларингологии, детской оториноларингологии, детской стоматологии Ташкентского педиатрического
медицинского института

Page Maker | Верстка | Саҳифаловчи: Хўршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

МУНДАРИЖА | СОДЕРЖАНИЕ | CONTENT

1. Kh.P. Kamilov, D.J.Kahharova, S.Sh.Sheralieva, N.I.Ubaydullaeva, A.Ye.Buriev TO THE ISSUE OF MALIGNANCY OF ORAL LEUKOPLAKIA.....	6
2. Kh.P. Kamilov, A.A. Kadirbaeva, Sh. N. Dadamukhamedov TREATMENT OF ORAL LICHEN PLANUS – MODERN APPROACH.....	12
3. Soleeva Sitara Shaxobovna EFFECT OF ROSUVASTATIN AND ITS COMBINATION WITH FENOFIBRIC ACID ON PRO-INFLAMMATORY CYTOKINES IN ELDERLY PATIENTS AFTER ENDOVASCULAR INTERVENTION.....	17
4. Shodiev Ulmas Mustafievich THE LEVEL OF EXPRESSION OF CD3(2GV6) and CD20(L26) MARKERS IN THE CELLS OF URINARY BLADDER POLYPS AND PAPILLOMA TISSUES.....	25
5. X. A. Rashidova POSSIBILITIES OF CLINICAL AND LABORATORY AND INSTRUMENTAL STUDIES IN NON – ALCOHOLIC FATTY LIVER DISEASE.....	31
6. Jo‘raev Nozim Shamsiddinovich, Sherali Qo‘zievich Hakimov SURGICAL TREATMENT OF UNSTABLE DIAPHYSAL FRACTURES OF THE CARPLES IN CHILDREN AND ADOLESCENTS METHODS OF TREATMENT.....	36
7. Akilov Khabibulla Ataullevich, Ibadov Raufbek Ravshanovich LABORATORY FEATURES OF COVID-19 ASSOCIATED CARDIOVASCULAR SYNDROME.....	40
8. Latipova Sitara Bakhodirovna REVIEWING CLINICAL AND THERAPEUTIC STUDIES AND TREATMENTS OF ORAL MUCOSA AFTER CHEMOTHERAPY.....	49
9. Djumaev Akmal Ubaidullaevich, Eshbaev Erkin Abdukhalimovich FEATURES OF HISTOCHEMICAL METHODS IN PATHOMORPHOLOGY OF CONGENITAL HEART DISEASES.....	53
10. Tulaboeva G.M., Sagatova H.M., Talipova Y.Sh., Abdukadirova N.M., Husanov A.A., Yuldashev N.P. CLINICAL EFFICACY OF COMBINED PREPARATION OF L-ARGININE AND LEVOCARNITINE IN ELDERLY PATIENTS WITH CORONARY HEART DISEASE AND DIABETES MELLITUS.....	59

**Tulaboeva G.M.,
Sagatova H.M.,
Talipova Y.Sh.,
Abdukadirova N.M.,
Husanov A.A.,
Yuldashev N.P.**

Center for development of professional qualification
of medical workers Department of Cardiology and
Gerontology with a course in interventional cardiology and
arrhythmology, Republic of Uzbekistan, Tashkent.
y.Talipova@mail.ru

CLINICAL EFFICACY OF COMBINED PREPARATION OF L-ARGININE AND LEVOCARNITINE IN ELDERLY PATIENTS WITH CORONARY HEART DISEASE AND DIABETES MELLITUS

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8228950>

ABSTRACT

From the point of view of the pathophysiology of cardiovascular diseases, metabolic correction is a reasoned approach. The postulate that asserts that the contracting heart is in dire need of energy fuel is beyond doubt. Metabolic therapy (MT) of cardiology is understood to improve energy metabolism in the heart muscle by pharmacological control of the processes of energy formation and transfer at the cardiomyocyte level without affecting coronary blood flow and systemic hemodynamics. In principle, two main directions of MT can be distinguished – optimization of the processes of formation and energy consumption, as well as normalization of the balance between the intensity of free radical oxidation and antioxidant protection.

Keywords: cardiovascular diseases, arterial hypertension, coronary heart disease, chronic heart failure, metabolic therapy, L-arginine, levocarnitine.

**Тулабоева Г.М.,
Сагатова Х.М.,
Талипова Ю.Ш.,
Абдукадирова Н.М.,
Хусанов А.А.,
Юлдашев Н.П.**

Кафедра кардиологии и геронтологии, интервенционной
кардиологии и аритмологии Центра развития профессиональной
квалификации медицинских работников
y.Talipova@mail.ru

КЛИНИЧЕСКАЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ КОМБИНИРОВАННОГО ПРЕПАРАТА L-АРГИНИНА И ЛЕВОКАРНИТИНА У БОЛЬНЫХ ПОЖИЛОГО ВОЗРАСТА С ИШЕМИЧЕСКОЙ БОЛЕЗНЬЮ СЕРДЦА И САХАРНЫМ ДИАБЕТОМ

АННОТАЦИЯ

С точки зрения патофизиологии сердечно-сосудистых заболеваний метаболическая коррекция является аргументированным подходом. Тот постулат, который в настоящее время утверждает, что сокращающееся сердце остро нуждается в энергетическом топливе, в настоящее время не вызывает сомнений. Под метаболической терапией (МТ) кардиологии понимают улучшение энергетического метаболизма в сердечной мышце путем фармакологического управления процессами образования и переноса энергии на уровне кардиомиоцитов без влияния на коронарный кровоток и системную гемодинамику. Принципиально можно выделить два основных направления МТ – оптимизацию процессов образования и расхода энергии, а также нормализацию баланса между интенсивностью свободнорадикального окисления и антиоксидантной защитой.

Ключевые слова: сердечно-сосудистые заболевания, артериальная гипертензия, ишемическая болезнь сердца, хроническая сердечная недостаточность, метаболическая терапия, L-аргинин, левокарнитин.

Тулабоева Г.М.,
Сагатова Х.М.,
Талипова Ю.Ш.,
Абдукадилова Н.М.,
Хусанов А.А.,
Юлдашев Н.П.

Тиббиет ходимларнинг касбий малакасини ривожлантириш
маркази кардиология ва геронтология, интервенцион
кардиология ва аритмология курси билан кафедраси
y.Talipova@mail.ru

КОРОНЕР ЮРАК КАСАЛЛИГИ ВА ҚАНДЛИ ДИАБЕТ БИЛАН ОҒРИГАН КЕКСА БЕМОРЛАРДА L-АРГИНИН ВА ЛЕВОКАРНИТИННИНГ КОМБИНАЦИЯЛАНГАН ПРЕПАРАТИНИНГ КЛИНИК САМАРАДОРЛИГИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Юрак-қон томир касалликларининг патофизиологияси нуктаи назаридан метаболик терапия асосли ёндашувдир. Ҳозирги вақтда қисқарувчи юрак энергия ёқилғисига жуда муҳтож эканлигини тасдиқловчи постулат, шубҳасиздир. Кардиологияда метаболик терапия - бу коронар қон оқими ва тизимли гемодинамикага таъсир қилмасдан кардиомиоцитлар даражасида энергия ҳосил бўлиш ва узатиш жараёнларини фармакологик назорат қилиш орқали юрак мушакларидаги энергия алмашинувини яхшилашдир. Асосан, МТ нинг иккита асосий йўналиши мавжуд- энергия ишлаб чиқариш ва унинг истеъмоли жараёнларини оптималлаштириш ҳамда эркин радикал оксидланиш интенсивлиги билан антиоксидант химоя ўртасидаги мувозанатни нормаллаштириш.

Калит сўзлар: юрак-қон томир касалликлари, артериал гипертензия, юрак ишемик касаллиги, сурункали юрак етишмовчилиги, метаболик терапия, L-аргинин, левокарнитин.

Introduction. Due to the fact that in recent years there has been an evolution in the understanding of the pathogenesis of CHD, the treatment of patients with CHD is also changing. The modern strategy of IHD treatment emphasizes coronary blood flow, restoration of endothelial dysfunction, and maintenance of energy processes at the level of cardiomyocytes. However, over the past few years, there has been significant progress in the study of the efficacy of metabolic therapy.

New evidence-based data have emerged to support the feasibility of metabolics. Metabolic therapy, on the one hand, will help to optimize myocardial energy exchange, increasing its viability, provide an antioxidant effect, which is extremely important for normal metabolism, and on the other hand, will help to restore the functional state of the endothelium, which is one of the key factors affecting the course of atherosclerotic lesions of the vascular channel. Endothelial dysfunction is primarily an imbalance between the production of vasodilatory, angioprotective, antiproliferative factors on the one hand (prostacyclin, tissue plasminogen activator, C-type natriuretic peptide, endothelial hyperpolarizing factor), and vasoconstrictive, prothrombotic, and proliferative factors on the other hand (endothelin, superoxide anion, thromboxane A, tissue plasminogen activator inhibitor) [2, 3, 4, 9].

Today endothelial dysfunction is considered a key point in the pathogenesis of atherosclerosis. Violation of vasodilatory activity of peripheral vessels is one of the numerous manifestations of endothelial dysfunction, which is sharply reduced in patients with AH, up to the development of vasoconstrictor reactions, which subsequently entails an inadequate response of the vascular bed and contributes to a steady increase in blood pressure (BP). The latter factor leads to target organ damage. The development of complications accompanies it, including left ventricular hypertrophy, stroke, myocardial infarction, chronic renal failure, etc. [1, 8, 17, 18]. [1, 8, 17, 18, 19]

Regarding the energy supply of cardiomyocytes, we know that the main source of ATP in cardiac muscle is fatty acids and carbohydrates. However, the conversion of these macronutrients into biological energy (ATP) is only possible in the presence of micronutrients such as coenzyme Q10, thiamine, riboflavin, L-carnitine, taurine, L-arginine, and other amino acids that function as major cofactors for ATP synthesis and transport, as well as substances that support physiologic cardiac function. Evidence-based medicine strongly suggests that metabolic therapy for cardiovascular disease should be directed toward restoring stores of L-carnitine, L-arginine. [5, 6, 23, 27]

Purpose of work: To evaluate the efficacy of combined preparation of L-arginine and levocarnitine (Levart, BILLUR PHARM LUX) in elderly patients with stable angina pectoris and diabetes mellitus.

Material and methods: 60 patients were included in the study and divided into 2 groups: main group (MG) - mean age $62,5 \pm 0,9$ years, control group (CG) - $63,4 \pm 1,1$ years, with a verified diagnosis of CHD, stable angina pectoris FC II, III, diabetes mellitus type II, CHS. The follow-up period was 6 weeks. All patients received standard therapy. In addition to standard therapy, the main group's patients received a combined preparation of L - arginine and levocarnitine in the form of an infusion of 100.0 ml of solution once a day for 10 days.

Inclusion criteria in the study: patients who signed informed consent, aged over 60 years, with the diagnosis of CHD complicated by moderately low and preserved CHF with moderately low and preserved EF and diabetes mellitus.

Exclusion criteria: decompensated CHF, decompensation of diabetes mellitus, severe liver and kidney dysfunction, oncologic diseases, intolerance to the drug.

All patients were taking as standard therapy: beta-blockers, IAPP or sartans, calcium antagonists, statins, antiaggregants, hypoglycemic drugs and nitrates when indicated. Both groups were clinically comparable and there were no significant differences in treatment between the groups.

Statistical analysis was performed using the statistical software package "SPSS 11.0". The obtained data were described as $M \pm SD$ (M-arithmetic mean, SD-standard deviation) or $M \pm m$ (m-standard error of the mean). Statistical significance of the obtained results when comparing mean values was determined by Student's t-test with the calculation of the probability of error (P) when checking the normality of distribution by standard methods.

Results and Discussion. All patients underwent general clinical laboratory investigations, lipid spectrum analysis, carbohydrate metabolism, coagulogram, and creatinine control with GFR, ECG, EchoCG determination. Comparative analysis of initial laboratory and instrumental data indicates that the indicators of the main and control groups have no statistically significant differences (Table 1).

Table 1.

Indicators of laboratory and instrumental methods of investigation of IBS and DM elderly patients (initial data)

Indicator	M+m	
	Main group N=30	Control group N=30
Mid age	62,5±0,9	63,4 ±1,1
BMI, kg/m ²	28,8±0,5	28,5±0,53
MBP, mm. Hg	140,1±2,3	138,6±1,7
MAP, mm. Hg	89,3±1,2	86,8±1,1
EF %	49,8±1,7	50±1,7
GFR ml/min/1.73m ²	60,1±1,2	59,6±1,5
PTI	96±1,1	97,4±0,6
Fibrinogen	3392,0±95	3389±94,2
Total cholesterol, mmol/L	6,1±0,2	6,4±0,13
Triglycerides, mmol/L	1,34±0,11	1,30±0,3
LDL-C, mmol/L	3,1± 0,21	2,9± 1,0
HDL-C, mmol/L	1,15±0,13	1,10± 1,12
HbA1c, % ave.	8,9±0,32	8,3±0,27

The analysis of the obtained data on lipid metabolism shows that the patients of the main group have more pronounced positive dynamics concerning Total Cholesterol, LDL and HDL indicators, the changes of which have a reliable character. Thus, OX decreased from 6.1 to 4.7 mmol/l, and LDL indicators decreased from 3.1 mmol/l to 2.2 mmol/l. The increase in HDL level is also significant, with an increase from 1.15 mmol to 1.65 mmol/l (Fig.1).

Note: *p<0,05 reliability of differences concerning initial data

Figure 1: Blood lipid metabolism indices in patients in the main group

In patients of the control group, there is a positive dynamics in the reduction of TC level from 6.4 mmol/l to 5.6 mmol/l, although these changes are not significant. The changes were insignificant on the part of LDL, TG and HDL indicators (Fig. 2). In our research when studying the level of glycated hemoglobin HbA1 in serum at the beginning of the study, the initial data between the groups had no statistically significant differences. In patients of the control group in the first study, this index amounted to $8.3 \pm 0.27\%$, and in patients of the main group - $8.9 \pm 0.32\%$. Analysis of the obtained data after the therapy in patients of both groups shows positive dynamics, which is reliable ($p < 0.05$). It should be noted that in the patients of the main group, the decrease in HbA1 level is 18% greater compared to the control group (Fig.1,2).

Note: * $p < 0.05$ reliability of differences with baseline data

Figure 2:

Blood lipid metabolism in patients in the control group

Note: * $p < 0.05$ reliability of differences with baseline data, $P < 0.05$ - after therapy

Figure 3:

Hemodynamic parameters in the examined patients

Intracardiac hemodynamic parameters had similar trends during the observation period. Thus, in patients of both groups, there is a slight increase in EF, which is statistically unreliable. But, detailed analysis shows that in patients who received combined preparation of L-arginine and

levocarnitine against the background of standard therapy, contractility improved by 5,9 % more ($p < 0,05$). Comparative analysis of CAD and DA parameters reveals positive dynamics in patients of both groups. But statistically significant changes ($p < 0.05$) in terms of CAD and DA reduction are observed in patients of the main group (Fig.3).

Note: * $p < 0.05$ reliability of differences about baseline data, $P < 0.05$ - after therapy

Figure 4: Analysis of parameters of glomerular filtration rate (GFR) and prothrombin index (PI) in the examined patients.

Also, the analysis of the effect of the therapy on the glomerular filtration rate indicates a possible additional nephroprotective effect of the combined preparation of L-arginine and levocarnitine. In patients of the main group, there is a significant increase in the glomerular filtration rate ($p < 0.05$). The analysis of the obtained data of the prothrombin index revealed statistically reliable positive dynamics in patients of both groups, with more pronounced changes in patients of the main group (Fig.4).

The analysis of fibrinogen data, one of the main indicators of coagulogram, also reveals that positive changes are observed in patients of both groups and they are reliable, but in patients of the main group, fibrinogen decreases by 2.6% more in comparison with the control group and they are more reliable (Fig.5).

Note: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.05$ reliability of differences with baseline data, $P < 0.05$ - after therapy.

Figure 5.

Dynamics of fibrinogen level reduction after therapy

Note: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.05$ reliability of differences with baseline data, P{T - after therapy, OG - basic group, CG - control group.

Figure 6. Dynamics of reduction in the number of angina pectoris attacks (APA) after therapy

At the same time, the dynamics of observation of the clinical efficacy of the therapy in patients of the main and control groups shows a decrease in the number of angina attacks in patients of both groups. In patients of the main group, who received Levart on the background of standard therapy, the number of angina attacks decreased by 20% and has a more reliable character (Fig.6).

Note: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.05$ reliability of differences with baseline data, A/T - after therapy, MG - main group, CG - control group.

Figure 7. Dynamics of decrease in the number of nitroglycerin tablets (NNT) after the therapy.

The analysis of dynamics of nitroglycerin tablet number reduction after the therapy also indicates more pronounced positive dynamics in patients of the main group (Fig.7). Antianginal effect

after the treatment in both groups was due to the use of standard therapy drugs. Still, the available reliable difference between the groups, characterized by a reliable decrease of CPS by 20% more and a reliable decrease of CTN by 12% more, indicates the investigated drug's antianginal efficacy and its positive influence on the course of CHD.

Thus, combined preparation of L-arginine and levocarnitine improves the clinical course of angina pectoris and improves the patient's quality of life by reducing the number of angina attacks and the number of nitroglycerin tablets consumed. Also, this drug has a beneficial effect on lipid and carbohydrate metabolism, nephroprotective property and a positive effect on coagulogram parameters.

Conclusion: Considering all the above-mentioned and taking into account a good safety and tolerability profile, the use of combined preparation of L-arginine and levocarnitine (Levart BILLUR PHARM LUX) in complex therapy of CHD patients allows for improvement in the quality of life and prognosis of the disease and optimize the treatment of CHD.

References:

1. Ageev F.T. Correction of endothelial function is the key to the success of treatment of cardiovascular diseases / F.T. Ageev // Heart. Journal for practicing physicians -2003.-№1- P.22-26.
2. Arginine in medical practice / Yu. Stepanov, I.N.Kononov, A.I.Zhurbina, A.Y.Filippova // Journal of the Academy of Medical Sciences of Ukraine - 2004.-№10(1) - P.340-352
3. Babushkina A.V. L-arginine from the point of view of evidence-based medicine // Ukrainian Medical Journal - 2009.-№6 (74) - p. 1-5./www.umj.com.ua/
4. The value of L-arginine in the treatment of patients with cardiovascular pathology / M.I. Lutai, V.V. Bugayenko, O.I. Moiseenko, L.O. Mushtenko, V.A. Slobodsky // Ukrainian Cardiology Journal - 2011.- №4.- P.98-110.
5. Cardiology: national guide / edited by E.V. Shlyakhto - 2nd ed.
6. Konopleva L.F. L-arginine in coronary heart disease: research continues / L.F. Konopleva, E.V. Andreev // Therapy. - 2010.- №10(51).- pp.64-68
8. The role of endothelial dysfunction in the genesis of cardiovascular diseases / V.N. Elsky, N.T. Vatutin, N.V. Kalinkina, A.M. Salakhova // Journal of the Academy of Medical Sciences of Ukraine. 2008 - №14(1) - P.51-62.
9. Slobodskyi V.A. Advantages of combined infusion and oral form of L-arginine in treating patients with stable angina pectoris // Zdorovye Ukrainy. - 2010. - №2-3. - P.17-20. Sizova Zh.M., Shikh E.V., Makhova A.A. Application of L-carnitine in general medical practice. Therapeutic archive. 2019; 91 (1): 114-20.
10. Efficacy of the drug tivortin in the treatment of patients with stable angina pectoris / Lutai YA, Kryuchkova ON, Itskova EA, Lebed EI // Crimean therapeutic journal.2013.-№1(20).-P.63-69
11. Boger R.H. The pharmacodynamics of L-arginine // J. Nutr. - 2007.- №137 (6 Suppl.2) -p.1650-1655.
12. Davignon J. Role of endothelial dysfunction in atherosclerosis / J. Davignon, P. Ganz//Circulation. - 2004. - Vol.109. - P.27-32.
13. Division of Cardiovascular Diseases and Internal Medicine. Mayo Clinic College of Medicine, Rochester, Minn 55905, USA. Current and future treatment strategies for refractory angina // Mayo Clin. Proc.-2004.-Vol.79(10). -P.1284-1292
14. Efficacy and safety of oral L-arginine in acute myocardial infarction. Results of the multicenter, randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled ARAMI pilot trial/B.Bednarz, T.Jaxa-Chamiec, P.Maciejewski et al.// Kardiol. Pol. -2005.-Vol.62(5)-P.421-427.
15. Lubos E. Role of oxidative stress and nitric oxide in atherothrombosis/E.Lubos, D.E.Handy, J.Loscalzo//Front. Biosci.-2009.- Vol.13.-P.5323-5344.

16. 2013 ESC guidelines on the management of stable coronary artery disease. The Task Force on managing stable coronary artery disease of the European Society of Cardiology // *Eur.Heart J.* - 2013. - Vol.34. - p.2949-3003
17. Marunych RY, Gornytyska OV, Gudzenko AV et al. (2021). The role of endothelium in regulating blood aggregation in normal atherosclerosis and hypertension. *Physiol. journal*, Vol. 67, No. 3.
18. Canto J. G., Kiefe C.I., Rogers W. J. et al. (2011). Number of coronary heart disease risk factors and mortality in patients with first myocardial infarction. *JAMA*. Nov 16; 306(19): 2120-7. doi: 10.1001/jama.2011.1654.
19. Nilsson P. M. Early vascular aging (EVA): consequences and prevention. *Vasc Health Risk Manag.*; 4: 547-52. doi: doi.org/10.2147/VHRM.S1094.
20. Schmitt M., Avolio A., Qasem A. et al. (2005). Basal NO locally modulates human iliac arterial function in vivo. *Hypertension*. Jul; 46(1): 227-31. doi: 10.1161/01.HYP.0000164581.39811.bd.
21. Schillaci G, Verdecchia P, Porcellati C, et al. (2000). Continuous relationship between left ventricular mass and cardiovascular risk in essential hypertension. *Hypertension*. Feb; 35(2): 580-6. doi: 10.1161/01.hyp.35.2.580.
22. Tomiyama H, Ishizu T, Kohro T, et al. (2018). Longitudinal association among endothelial function, arterial stiffness and subclinical organ damage in hypertension. *Int J Cardiol*. Feb 15; 253: 161-166. doi: 10.1016/j.ijcard.2017.11.022.
23. Perticone F., Ceravolo R., Candigliota M. et al. (2001). Obesity and body fat distribution induce endothelial dysfunction by oxidative stress: protective effect of vitamin C. *Diabetes*. Jan; 50(1): 159-65. doi: 10.2337/diabetes.50.1.159.
24. Sokolova LK, Pushkarev VM, Tronko MD (2019). L-arginine in normal and pathology. *Endocrinology*. Vol. 24. no. 4. 373-385. doi: 10.31793/1680-1466.2019.24-4.373.
25. Weckman A.M., McDonald C.R., Baxter J.B. et al. (2019). Perspective: L-arginine and L-citrulline Supplementation in Pregnancy: A Potential Strategy to Improve Birth Outcomes in Low-Resource Settings. *Adv Nutr*. Sep 1; 10(5): 765-777. doi: 10.1093/advances/nmz015.
26. Mishchenko LA (2020). Organ-protective capabilities of L-arginine in the treatment of patients with arterial hypertension. "Health of Ukraine of the 21st Century" № 23 (492).
27. Sepandi M., Abbaszadeh S., Qobady S. et al. (2019). Effect of L-Arginine supplementation on lipid profiles and inflammatory markers: A systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Pharmacol Res*. Oct; 148: 104407. doi: 10.1016/j.phrs.2019.104407.
28. Yin W.H., Chen J.W., Tsai C. et al. (2005). L-arginine improves endothelial function and reduces LDL oxidation in stable coronary artery disease patients. *Clin Nutr*. Dec; 24 (6): 988-97. doi: 10.1016/j.clnu.2005.07.003.
29. Kutovoy A. B., Lyulko I.V., Amro A. et al. (2014). L-Arginine in complex therapy of chronic ischemia of lower limbs in atherosclerosis. *Serce i sudini*, No. 3, P. 89-92.
30. Lekakis J.P., Papathanassiou S., Papaioannou T.G. et al. (2002). Oral L-arginine improves endothelial dysfunction in patients with essential hypertension. *Int J Cardiol*. Dec; 86 (2-3): 317-23. doi: 10.1016/s0167-5273(02)00413-8.
31. West S.G., Likos-Krick A., Brown P. et al. (2005). Oral L-arginine improves hemodynamic responses to stress and reduces plasma homocysteine in hypercholesterolemic men. *J Nutr*. Feb; 135 (2): 212-7. doi: 10.1093/jn/135.2.212.
32. Bahadoran Z., Mirmiran P., Tahmasebinejad Z. et al. (2016). Dietary L-arginine intake and the incidence of coronary heart disease: Tehran lipid and glucose study. *Nutr Metab (Lond)*. Mar 15; 13: 23. doi: 10.1186/s12986-016-0084-z.
33. Xu Y., Jiang W., Chen G. et al. L-carnitine treatment of insulin resistance: A systematic review and meta-analysis // *Adv. Clin. Exp. Med.* – 2017. – Vol. 26 (2). – P. 333–338. doi: 10.17219/acem/61609.

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

4 ЖИЛД, 4 СОН

ЎЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ

ТОМ 4, НОМЕР 4

UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

VOLUME 4, ISSUE 4

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz

Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,

Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz

Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz

ООО Тадқиқот город Ташкент,

улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz

Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000